

**HISTORY AND EVOLUTION OF TRADITIONAL NEWSPAPER
JOURNALISM**

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In this day and age of increasing information flow, it is inconceivable to imagine our lives without the media. This article provides an overview of the development of modern newspapers, on the other hand, is about conventional newspapers and their evolution, which have not yet lost their value and relevance in people's lives. The evolution of the media has been fraught with concerns and challenges, but it has gone a long way to the present day. The objective of this article is to demonstrate the history of the origin of newspapers, their significance in the development of nations' languages and cultures, to inform mankind about current events throughout the world, and their contribution to literacy.

Keywords: Acta diurna, tipao, printing machine, avvisi, La Gazette, newspapers, characteristics of newspaper, value of newspaper in society

A newspaper is a periodical publication that contains written information about current events. Newspapers have always been an essential aspect of civil society, providing individuals with information, bringing them together around events and causes. They can cover a wide range of topics, including politics, business, sports, and art, and they frequently include features such as opinion pieces, weather predictions, and evaluations of local businesses. From the creation of the printing press to the introduction of the Digital Age, the history of newspapers has gone a long way and is still being written.

The origins of written news, which were the ancestors of newspapers, may be traced back to the Roman Empire. Most historians credit the Romans with inventing regular written news bulletins. It all began with ancient Roman scrolls dubbed "Daily

events of the Roman people" were first published in 59 BC and they are called "Acta diurna" (Latin: Daily Acts, sometimes translated as Daily Public Records or poetically as Daily Gazette).¹ People carved them out of stone or metal in the beginning, later all of these "newspapers" were made by hand. They comprised chronicles of occurrences, births, deaths, and daily gossip. Julius Caesar launched the Acts of the Senate, an official magazine that published reports and reports from the authorities.

The tipao (pinyin: dǐbào; Wade-Giles: ti-pao), literally "reports from the [official] residences", was one of the early sample of newspaper and it was the first kinds of news journalism in China.² These were "palace reports or imperial bulletins" published by the government and meant for officials as early as 202 BC. Any public information might have been disseminated by posted announcements, forerunners to today's posters.

When it comes to speak about modern newspapers they were created in Europe. The modern newspaper owes virtually nothing to ancient media, such as the Roman Acta or Chinese experimental news bulletins. The forerunner of the newspaper emerged in Europe in this form - as a news sheet - in the middle of the 15th century, when German goldsmith Johannes Gutenberg built a printing machine with interchangeable and moveable letters³. Johannes Gutenberg's printing machine was a watershed moment in the history of the press. His movable-type press could reproduce high-quality printed documents at a pace of over 4000 pages per day. This ground-breaking machine lowered the cost of printed documents and made them affordable to the public. The first editions attributed to Johannes Gutenberg were small leaflet calendars and textbooks.

¹ Chisholm, Hugh, ed. (1911). "Acta Diurna". Encyclopedia Britannica. Vol. 1 (11th ed.). Cambridge University Press. p. 159

² Fang, H. (Ed.). (2012). Journalism in Ancient China. A history of journalism in china (pp.24-70). Honolulu, HI: Enrich Professional Publishing (S) Private Limited.

³ Nelson, Heming (11 February 1998). "A history of newspaper: Gutenberg's press started a revolution". The Washington Post.

Despite the fact moveable type printing had been known in eastern Asia since the 10th century, it was not reached to Europe. Although there existed a print industry in Europe, woodblock printing was a complicated and time-consuming process. Gutenberg's discovery resulted in a huge increase in speed and efficiency. By 1500, the printing press had spread across Europe, and publishers were widely disseminating news sheets.

Handwritten newspapers that were frequently disseminated in Venice, Italy in the 16th century appear to be another first direct predecessor of the contemporary newspaper. Venice was the center of global trade, and hence of information. In Venice, the "avvisi" or gazettes first emerged as Venetian news sheets.⁴ They were written by hand and centered on politics and military battles. Some of their issues even made it to London.

It took another two hundred years for newspapers to take on the appearance we know today. On May 30, 1631, the first issue of the La Gazette was published.⁵ The name "La Gazette" was drawn from a tiny silver coin (Gazzetta) given by Venetians for handwritten newspapers. On Fridays, the Gazette was published on four pages, measuring 23 by 15 cm. The number of pages was then extended to 12, and pictures were included. After some time the aristocrat Theophrastus Renaudeau got a patent for delivering news throughout France for "La Gazette". Each year's issues were compiled into a single volume titled "Annual Collection". "The political importance of "La Gazette" was such that King Louis XIII of France, as well as Cardinal Richelieu, wrote personal letters to it.

The two oldest European newspapers that have survived were both published weekly in Germany in 1609: "Aller Furnemmen" was published in Strasbourg by Johann Carolus, and the other, "Aviso Relation oder Zeitung" was published, most likely in Wolfenbüttel, by Lukas Schulte. The printed newspaper Newspapers started

⁴ Jerilyn McIntyre, "The 'Avvisi' of Venice: Toward an Archaeology of Media Forms." *Journalism History* 1987 p68

⁵ Raphael Levy (1929). "The Daily Press in France". *The Modern Language Journal*. Blackwell Publishing. **13** (4): 294–303

to spread throughout Europe in a short period of time.⁶ Basel (1610), Frankfurt and Vienna (1615), Hamburg (1616), Berlin (1617) and Amsterdam (1618) all had printed weeklies. In 1665, Oxford issued the first English newspaper. The Oxford Gazette was renamed the London Gazette after it relocated to London in 1666. In 1631, France had its own newspaper. Amsterdam, a center of international trade and political tolerance, began exporting weekly newspapers in 1620.

In the first newspapers, messages were published in approximately the same form in which they fell into the hands of the publisher. The word "newspaper" was first used in England in 1670.⁷ In London, one of the first initiatives to improve the system was to make incoming communications legible.

The newspaper is distinguished by a clearly articulated and plainly expressed function of influence or expressiveness. These two tasks are not separated in newspaper speech. "Genuine" newspaper should include four characteristics:

- public accessible;
- released on a regular basis (daily, weekly, monthly, etc.);
- current, up-to-date material;
- covers a wide range of issues (politics, events, entertainment, sports, etc.)

The theoretical direction of the newspaper's content is expressed through the employment of a range of linguistic tools, including lexical and syntactic aspects of scientific discourse. The newspaper serves several purposes, including informative, educational, organizational, and hedonistic purposes (entertaining). The primary mission of the newspaper, however, remains propaganda and information, as well as information influence. The proportion of techniques and procedures for producing expressiveness in journalistic discourse is relatively high when compared to other functional styles.

⁶ Weber, Johannes (2006). "Strassburg, 1605: The Origins of the Newspaper in Europe". German History.

⁷ Matthias A. Shaaber, "The History of the First English Newspaper." *Studies in Philology* 29.4 (1932): 551–587.

During the twentieth century, news transmission progressed from being nearly an afterthought to supporting 24-hour media sources. Satellites enabled the timely transmission of foreign news, making the technology important for news development. Today, the newspaper industry continues to face challenges as the Digital Age threatens the survival of the newspaper. However, the emergence of online newspapers and their popularity among Internet users, as well as the fact that print versions of newspapers are still published, demonstrate that newspapers remain firmly rooted in society.

When it comes to speak about the importance of newspapers, they have a vital role in promoting commerce, trade, and business. Large corporations and industrial firms market their products by placing large advertising in newspapers. Newspapers' vital content and material also include classified advertising, major public announcements, and public notifications. Sports, educational and campus news, dance, theater, cultural events, and fine arts are all essential components of all prominent publications.

Nowadays newspaper has shifted toward giving in-depth coverage, analysis, and opinion on a wide range of current events. The quality of newspaper coverage of commercial concerns, the arts, and social issues is becoming increasingly essential in most Western countries as publishers cope with more intelligent consumers. Even as they change to the fashions and interests of the day, newspapers continue to serve as a venue for serious discussion, a medium for creative expression, and a defender of the written word.

In brief, the demise of the newspaper has long been foretold, yet despite competition from radio, television, and now the Internet, newspapers continue to grow globally since they serve crucial social purposes in successful civilizations. To survive and prosper, newspapers are altering their goods to customer demand. Newspapers, as a brand, continue to have a large following. They are so vital to a flourishing society that, despite or because of changes in reading habits and technology, a timely and easily available news offering will be successful.

References

1. Chisholm, Hugh, ed. (1911). "Acta Diurna". *Encyclopedia Britannica*. Vol. 1 (11th ed.). Cambridge University Press. p. 159
2. Fang, H. ed. (2012). *Journalism in Ancient China. A history of journalism in China*, pp.24-70. Honolulu, HI: Enrich Professional Publishing (S) Private Limited.
3. Jerilyn McIntyre, (1987). "The 'Avvisi' of Venice: Toward an Archaeology of Media Forms." *Journalism History* p68
4. Nelson, Heming (11 February 1998). "A history of newspaper: Gutenberg's press started a revolution". *The Washington Post*.
5. Matthias A. Shaaber, "The History of the First English Newspaper." *Studies in Philology* 29.4 (1932): 551–587.
6. Raphael Levy (1929). "The Daily Press in France". *The Modern Language Journal*. Blackwell Publishing. **13** (4): 294–303
7. Weber, Johannes (2006). "Strassburg, 1605: The Origins of the Newspaper in Europe". *German History*.